

Supporting Information

3D Morphology of Iron Oxide Nanoparticles with Reactive Concave Surfaces – a Compressed Sensing- Electron Tomography (CS-ET) Approach

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Figure S1 High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HRTEM) image of a group of concave NPs. The NPs are seen to have single crystalline structure.

Figure S2 Otsu segmentation of various orthoslices through the SIRT (top) and CS-ET (bottom) reconstructions obtained from a tilt series of 27 projections. The optical axis is oriented vertically.

Figure S3 Otsu binarisation of the same orthoslice, obtained with SIRT (top) and CS-ET (bottom), from 27 (a-d), 13 (b-e) and 9 (c-f) projections. The optical axis is oriented vertically.